

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

MANAGEMENT OF THE ORGANISATIONS OF BUSINESS PROCESSES - THE IMPORTANT FACTOR IN REALISATION OF STRATEGIC PROBLEMS OF DEVELOPMENT AT THE PRESENT STAGE

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Abstract

Article is devoted research decisions of problems of vector optimisation of management by human resources and of search of the compromise within the limits of realisation of strategic problems of development at the present stage.

Keywords: the human capital, business processes, management of human resources.

Market conditions of managing show increased requirements to a role and value of the human capital in the national purposes and strategic problems of development that causes shift in the conditions of an industrially-economic paradigm of business – from based redistribution of the capital, movement of labour on manufacture of the goods and services and having in the actives financially tangible resources, to – to the economy non-material resources - intelligence, knowledge, "know-how" become which important active.

As non-material resources are initially personified and capable to integration on various levels of production, hence, it is necessary for economic science to develop the effective mechanism of management of human resources within the limits of realisation of strategic problems at the present stage of development.

Now human resources are understood not only as interaction of heads, management and the employees of the enterprise in common performing any work, but also as all structure of interaction in the company. The system of strategic operation of business, business of mutual relation with experts, experts, advisers out of the enterprise, the scientific interests of employees realised in the form of publications is that it is possible to characterise as knowledge and the abilities belonging both the concrete person, and the enterprise as a whole.

The key competence of human and material resources allows the company to achieve steady competitive advantages.

Management of human resources takes place because transformation of the given capital to a product can be accompanied by increase and improvement of qualitative parametres of the most human capital.

The concept «the human capital» in 1962 was entered into a scientific turn(turnover) by the American economist, the expert in the theory of the finance of Frits Mahlup (Fritz Machlup), having connected this concept with an economic estimation of knowledge. [1]

Domestic scientists also investigated tendencies of increase of a role of the person in a modern society that has found reflexion in L.I.Abalkina, I.V.Bushmarina's works, Э.Д. Vilhovchenko, V.S.Gojlo, A.D.Kosmina, S.N.Yashin, etc.

The human capital includes the formed part of a manpower, knowledge, toolkit of intellectual and administrative work, inhabitancy and the labour activity, providing «model simultaneous investment, industrial and financial planning of programs of innovative development of region» [2].

Last circumstance causes necessity of consideration of various approaches to definition of theoretical concept of alternative management by human resources and workings out of author's lexicographic concept «management of the organisations of business processes», allowing, in the author's opinion, to order value of a target indicator of efficient control each business process according to which their choice is carried out.

According to the author, management of the organisations of the business processes based(founded) on perspective directions, the operating(working) processes connected about perfection business - and leaders to decrease in labour input, to improvement of quality of let out(released) production, automation and mechanisation of manufacture becomes the major active of national innovative projects.

Efficient control the organisations of business processes becomes the major competitive advantage of the companies, and, finally, - competitive advantage of national economy.

Management of the organisations of business processes transfers(carries) accent with the technical models of the organisation of work on антропоцентрическую, giving special attention to a problem of investments into the human capital, to development of a creative component of the worker.

Management of the organisations of business processes is effective a national stage of development the form of government an individual creative power of the worker included in system of innovative economy as a primary factor, work providing high dynamism, an intensification of social and economic progress of a society.

Thus, management of the organisations of business processes at a stage of the national purposes and strategic problems of development is considered(examined) as key, but not the separate, not isolated factor of

manufacture, and as the certain independent force giving to major factors of manufacture additional productive ability. That is, it is a question not of refusal of a role of "major factor" of manufacture veshchestvenno - the power capital and transition to another (intellectual), and about change of their parity (ratio) by criterion of dominating influence on economic growth, on increase of competitiveness and efficiency of functioning of the organisation in existing social and economic conditions.

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